

ACTIVITIES OF INSTITUTIONS WORKING IN THE COTTON SECTOR IN THE
TURKESTAN REGION (IN THE END OF 19TH AND THE BEGINNING OF THE 20TH
CENTURIES)

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Abstract: *In this article the activity of institutions working in the cotton sector in the Turkestan region in the 19th-beginning of the 20th centuries. The paper shows their role in the economic system of Turkestan, notes their advantages and disadvantages, common and distinctive features, peculiarities of organization.*

Keywords: *institutions, cotton, partnership, Turkestan, cotton-cleaning plants, firms*

One of the major institutions operating in the cotton sector of the Turkestan region was the Partnership of Yaroslavl Large Manufactory. The partnership was founded in 1858. In the mid-1880s, the partnership opened its offices in some towns of Central Asia. In Tashkent, there was a main office. The other offices were in Andijan, Bukhara, Kokand, Margilan, Namangan, Merv and Skobelev (Ferghana).⁹⁸

In fact, The Partnership had some cotton plantations in different parts of Central Asia with an area of 2750 tithes of land. For example, in 1898, the largest cotton farm was located in the village of Butakara, located 35 miles from the city of Andijan.⁹⁹

Apart from it, the Partnership owned 16 cotton-cleaning plants in Turkestan. Plants and offices of the cotton purchase Partnership were located in Turkestan General Governorate, Bukhara Emirate and Khiva Khanates. Annually, the cotton purchased by the Partnership was hundreds of thousands of poods of raw cotton. For instance, during the period 1915-1916, 791638 poods and 13 pounds of cotton were bought. In 1915, the Partnership became part of monopolistic Besh Bosch (Five Heads).¹⁰⁰

The Board of the Partnership of Yaroslavl factory of large manufactory was located in Moscow and the main office was in Central Asia in Tashkent. The Fund No. 99 of the Ferghana State Archive of the Republic of Uzbekistan preserved materials related to the activities of the Partnership from 1888 to 1918. In the documentary

⁹⁸ I. Agafonova, N. A. Khalfin. Guidebook of the Central State Historical Archive of the UzSSR. Tashkent, 1948.

⁹⁹ Cotton management and government measures to improve and develop it in Central Asian properties of Russia: From the report on the visit of the Chief Division of the Department of Agriculture A. I. Knise in autumn of 1910. St. Petersburg: Kirshbaum, 1911.

¹⁰⁰ M. Vekselman. Rossijskij Monopolisticheskij I Inostrannyj Kapital v Srednej Aziikonec 19 nachalo 20 v- Tashkent: Fan. 1987.

sources, there was a correspondence with the board of the partnership and its offices along with statistics on the purchase, sale and transportation of cotton, on yield and processing, results about cotton cleaning, the situation in cotton markets, cotton samples and cotton mills.

It is needless to note that the Partnership of Yaroslavl Large Manufactory focused on American cotton culture not only for the needs of its factory but also for the distribution of good seeds to the indigenous population even if real American seeds were released by the Partnership from America in large quantities in this endeavor.

According to the sources, the transportation of cotton fiber by rail from Ferghana to Yaroslavl was carried out through the "Eastern Society of Commodity Warehouses" and the society "The Caucasus and Mercury". Before being loaded into the wagon, each cotton fibre bale in front of the transporter representative was weighed, the serial number was set, and then loaded into the cars. Upon the arrival of the cargo on the railway to Yaroslavl for the acceptance at the factory, a kip was needed again and the invoice showed the weight of the goods in poods and pounds. For example, the invoice to the receipt No. 180509 for 1903 stated that "the Eastern society of commodity warehouses" from the Andijan office of the Partnership had accepted the goods as Egyptian cotton of 1st grade (Andijan) marked 7011 with a total of 55 kip (469 poods). According to the plummet of the receipt No. 128550 - dated 1903 from Andizhan to Yaroslavl, "Caucasus and Mercury" - 55 kilos of cotton fiber were shipped by rail (470 poods).¹⁰¹

The accepted cotton from the companies were from the offices of the "Caucasus and Mercury" society which were to be sent from the warehouses of the society. According to information dated February 14, 1906, 51 wagons were accepted in Namangan, 13 cars in Kokand, and 1 car in Margilan. Each of them was 60 kip.¹⁰²

The Partnership management was interested in growing the cotton plantations from new early-ripening and fruit-bearing varieties of cotton. The letter of the Board of March 19, 1903 from Moscow to the Head Office in Tashkent informed 3 bags of American cottonseeds from the American Department of Agriculture was to be sent to Andijan for delivery to the Andreevsky farming association for the production of experimental crops.¹⁰³ The letter of the Main offices in Tashkent under No. 82 of 17 February, 1909 to the Kokand office, reported that one sack of cotton was sent through railways. The Mississippi Benders seeds with a fiber length of 29-30 mm and the seeds were prescribed by the Board from America. Since this cotton grew up on the banks of the Mississippi River, it was experimented in places where the soil was wetter. So, instruction was given to send the seeds to Margilan.¹⁰⁴

¹⁰¹ Administration of Ferghana oblast // TSGA RUz. F. II-99. Op. 1. D. 14. L. 29, 31.

¹⁰² The chancellery of the Turkestan General-Governor // TSGA RUz. D. 22. L. 206.

¹⁰³ Administration of Ferghana oblast TSGA RUz. D 14. L. 43

¹⁰⁴ The chancellery of the Turkestan General-Governor// TSGA RUz. D.53. L. 8

Nonetheless, there was an advance payment on the future harvest when buying raw cotton in advance from the Commissioners of the Partnership. For example, in the dispatch of a telegram from Kokand to the Board on March 24, 1903, it was reported:

"Kokand, all firms give out deposits", Gilenko.

"Many of our old loyal clients left us, allow me to give them twenty thousand, for the time being. The deposit was going to be made on time, there is no reason to be afraid of the future. Kurilov".¹⁰⁵

However, the dispatch from Andijan to the Board in the midst of cotton harvest, October 11, 1903 informed:

"Driving intensifies. Transfer the farm to Andijan for Kuva 4 hundred, Namangan 200, Margelan 100, Kokand a hundred thousand rubles. Prices are worth according to the previous a telegram. Kurilov".¹⁰⁶

It is needless to note that in case of a violation by the cotton supplier, the terms of the notarial agreement on receipt - a deposit made by a trustee of the Partnership- was enforced culminating in the damage caused by the deposit to be levied in court.

From the materials of the New Margelan District Court, an appeal from the trustee of the Moshkov Partnership in the persuit with Hashimbai Mir. Khamitova under the notarial contract for 1500 rubles could be found. The decision of the court chamber was in the favor of the Partnership.¹⁰⁷

The Partnership's field offices were constantly informed by the Head Office and the Board on all matters related to cotton farming. According to the letter No. 112 dated May 1, 1915, sent to the main office of the partnership from the Namangan office, it was stated that:

"On cotton crops: by the 1st of the month: The cotton crops are finished, the shoots are good. Weather it is clear, warm, favorable for sowing. There's plenty of water, except in the Chartaq region, where the area under crops for low water reduced by 30%. There were no harmful effects on cotton sowing and reseeding".¹⁰⁸

Besides cotton cleaning, the Partnership delivered cottonseeds to oil mills located in the Turkestan region. It was reflected in the letter sent from the Andijan office of the main office in Tashkent № 1 dated May 8, 1913. The letter was on the delivery of cottonseeds to the Turkestan Trade and Industrial Association "*K.M. Soloviev and Ko.*" (for the 1912/1913 season). In addition to cotton cleaning, it also had a number of oil maker factories in the Ferghana region.

According to the documents of Fund 19 of the Ferghana Regional Board pertaining to the delivery of information to the Department of Trade and Manufacturers for the activities of cotton mills in 1889, there is evidence from the list of the cotton mills that the plant was founded in 1888 in Namangan. In the following year, 34163 cotton poodswere cleaned at the plant. The fibers amounted to 273304

¹⁰⁵ The chancellery of the Turkestan General-Governor // TSGA RUz. D.14. L. 57, 103

¹⁰⁶ Ibid.

¹⁰⁷ The chancellery of the Turkestan General-Governor // TSGA RUz. I. 350. Op. 1. D. 2691. L. 2-3, 21.

¹⁰⁸ The chancellery of the Turkestan General-Governor // TSGA RUz. I.19. Op. 1. D. 87. L. 62.

rubles. 28 workers worked on four sixty-saws gins and on twin-screw press machines. The products were sold in the city of Yaroslavl.¹⁰⁹

In the materials of Fund 87 from the "Turkestan treasury chamber", the Partnership's cotton-cleaning plant in Butakara village started working in 1897 in Miley Izbaskent of the Andijan parish of the county. In 1901, the same plant was put into operation in the Kainar parish of the Kokand district.¹¹⁰

According to the documents of the Andijancounty landed presence, there was a cotton-cleaning plant in Uilyuk part of the old city of Andijan- at the street of Sharifbay- in 1911. There was also an office at the Karamulinsk street which also owned by the Partnership.¹¹¹

In the materials of the Fund of personal origin- pertaining to the activities of Richard Rikhardovich who managed the Turkestan Agricultural Experimental Station and the Turkestan Agricultural Society - there was valuable information on local and American cotton.

For example, according to the office of Andreyevskij farm of the Partnership of Yaroslavl factory of large manufactory in 1902, the yield of fibers from one pood of the first cotton harvest was Malachigit 13 pounds, Kara-chigit was 12.92, 12.5 for New Orleans Upland, and Kok-chigit ("Miracle") amounted 11.5 pounds.¹¹²

Hence, it can be concluded from the archival materials that the Partnership of Yaroslavl factory in the large manufactory space made a great contribution to the development of cotton production in the Turkestan region particularly in the Ferghana Valley. The Partnership created a number of cotton factories and warehouses, telegraph lines, railways in the region. Ferghana began to get involved in the economic life of Turkestan as well the Russian empire.

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4. F. 404 – Cotton Committee.

¹⁰⁹ The chancellery of the Turkestan General-Governor // TSGA RUz. D. 24006. L. 24–26.

¹¹⁰ Cotton Committee //TSGA RUz. I. 87. Op. 1. D. 26732. L. 35–36

¹¹¹ Cotton Committee //TSGA RUz. I. 614. Op. 1. D. 8. L. 35–36

¹¹² Cotton Committee //TSGA RUz. I. 2284. Op. 1. Д. 879. L. 2